

Embodied Knowledge in Digital Spaces: Towards Human-Centered Fabrication Formats

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Abstract

This research investigates the preservation of embodied knowledge and creative agency within digital fabrication processes and contexts. The historical division between conception and execution, intensified by industrialization, has been perpetuated in digital formats that prioritize geometric precision over tacit knowledge. While neo-craftspeople have adapted digital tools to their practices, current representation systems fail to capture the essence of making that characterizes craft processes. Through an experimental multi-modal computer vision pipeline implemented with pottery artisans, this study develops the .cft format, a time-based representation that preserves not just what was created, but how it emerged through hand movements, material interactions, and decision-making processes. By drawing from cross-cultural preservation models that prioritize adaptation over static conservation, this research proposes alternative digital fabrication paradigms that honor rather than erase the human dimensions of making. The findings suggest that true democratization of fabrication requires reimagining not just access to tools, but the fundamental relationship between maker, material, and technology in ways that reunite conception with execution and preserve the maker's voice throughout the creative process.

Keywords

craftsmanship, computer vision, digital fabrication, conservation, preservation, fab labs

1 Introduction

1.1 Historical Issue

The historical rupture between arts and crafts, rooted in ancient educational hierarchies and deepened by the industrial revolution, has reshaped how societies value human creative expression. The Spanish Baroque painter Antonio Palomino described this distinction accurately already in the eighteenth century: "In liberal art there is more contemplation than toil, and in mechanical art there is more toil than contemplation" (Beech, 2019). This divide relegated artisanship to the status of "illiberal" or mechanical arts, systematically stripping traditional making practices of the intellectual recognition and cultural prestige given to fine arts. The consequences of this distinction persist today in how we perceive, value, teach, and preserve human creative expression.

The industrial revolution intensified this degradation through the fragmentation of the creative process. This fragmentation manifested itself primarily in the division of labor, replacing the holistic knowledge of craftspeople with the repetition of isolated tasks, giving greater importance to productive efficiency over technical mastery and personal expression. American industrial engineer Frederick W. Taylor exemplified this approach through the development of scientific management, where he defined management as "knowing exactly what you want men to do and then seeing that they do it in the best and cheapest way" (Bunker Gilbreth, 1912). Although Taylor's approach proclaimed a supposed harmony between the economic interests of employers and workers, it transformed workers into mere executors of predefined and standardized operations. As Neil Gershenfeld notes, "the invention of industrial automation meant that a single machine could now make many things, but it also meant that a single worker who used to do

many things now did only one" (Gershenfeld, 2007). This change not only transformed the ways of production but also hurt the connection between conception and execution that characterized craft work, altering what philosopher Bruno Latour identifies as the distribution of agency in productive processes. Where craft traditions maintained what the author terms "symmetrical" relationships between human and non-human actors, in which materials, tools, and makers all participated in shaping outcomes, industrial division created hierarchical arrangements that concentrated decision-making agency in management while reducing workers to mere executors, resulting in a dehumanization of productive work.

During the last two centuries, different movements have responded to this dehumanization. From the direct resistance of Luddism against mechanization to the reformist proposals of the **Arts & Crafts** movement led by William Morris and John Ruskin, these responses shared a critical vision of industrialization and advocated for recovering the dignity of manual work. Morris argued that "*in almost all cases there is no empathy between the designer and the man who executes the design*" (Morris, 1884), identifying this separation as the origin of a cultural and productive problem.

1.2 Contemporary Context

It wasn't until the early 21st century that a different approach attempting to bridge this gap emerged. The personal fabrication movement initiated by Neil Gershenfeld at the **Massachusetts Institute of Technology** didn't start from nostalgia for traditional craft practices but from the democratization of productive capabilities. This approach represented paradoxically, "*a return to our industrial roots, before art separated from artisans, when production was done for individuals instead of masses*" (Gershenfeld, 2007), opening the way to a "craft renaissance" in the digital context.

Contemporary artisanship has shown how traditional practices can adapt and evolve by incorporating digital fabrication tools. Sociologist Richard Sennett argues in his work **The Craftsman** that the essence of craftsmanship does not simply reside in manual skill or material uses, but in a constant dialogue between concrete practices and thought. For the author, it represents a lasting, basic human impulse, "*the desire to do a job well for its own sake*" (Sennett, 2009). The obstacles and resistances that the artisan encounters during the interaction with materials and tools are precisely what encourage the development of skills and deep understanding.

This perspective can redefine the perception of digital fabrication spaces. Unlike the **Arts & Crafts** movement and Luddite resistance, which looked to preserve craft dignity through opposition to mechanization, personal fabrication represents a fundamentally different approach to reconnect conception and execution. **Fab Labs** and maker spaces are not simply places to access "advanced" digital fabrication technology, but *environments* where people can reestablish the connection between thought and action that characterizes the craft process through technology rather than in spite of it. These technologies are not mere auxiliary tools but extensions of the creator's body and mind, forming part of the creative process. As professor Lucy Suchman argues, these spaces become sites of expanded creative agency where human and technological capacities merge into what she terms "heterogeneously constituted human/nonhuman capacities for thought and action" (Suchman, 2009). In essence, the maker and their digital tools form a unified creative system where traditional boundaries between conceiver and executor, designer and fabricator, dissolve into collaborative making, achieving what Morris and Ruskin sought but through technological integration rather than rejection.

1.3 Preservation Challenge

Yet despite digital fabrication's potential to restore the thought to action unity of traditional crafts, the preservation of craft knowledge itself remains a critical challenge. Craftship falls into a cultural blind spot, often viewed as neither historically significant or aesthetically valuable enough to justify systematic preservation. This problem, which is aggravated by the limitations of current digital representation systems, forces to reconsider what it truly means to preserve a living cultural practice.

A fundamental problem is that the representation formats and technologies used in modern digital fabrication perpetuate the same division between design and manufacturing that originally separated the craftspeople from their work. As Gershenfeld points out, "*G-code and similar formats are the enemy because they enshrine a historical division of labor*" (Gershenfeld, 2023). These systems encode instructions for machines but do not capture the knowledge, decisions, or processes that constitute the true essence of craft knowledge. By focusing on final geometries and tool paths, these formats eliminate precisely the obstacles and resistances that Sennett identifies as crucial for the development of craft mastery.

1.4 Research Approach

The present investigation explores how digital fabrication spaces and technologies might help bridge rather than widen the historical gap between conception and execution in craft practices, contrary to what current digital fabrication practices have been doing. This research questions: **HOW CAN DIGITAL REPRESENTATION FORMATS, INSPIRED BY CRAFTS, PRESERVE CREATIVE AGENCY AND EMBODIED KNOWLEDGE IN DESIGN AND FABRICATION PROCESSES?**

To address this challenge, this work develops an experimental methodology based on computer vision techniques applied directly with pottery artisans. Pottery was selected as a case study because it offers visible material transformation where clay responds to pressure, movement, and technique, making the embodied knowledge of the artisan "visible" through material change. Using computer vision techniques including depth mapping, object segmentation, and hand tracking, this study aims to capture not just the final ceramic piece but the complete temporal journey of its creation.

Building on these captured temporal processes, the research culminates with the development of the *.cft* format, a time-based digital representation format that preserves how objects emerge through hand movements, material interactions, and decision-making processes. Unlike static 3D models that capture only final geometries, this format enables temporal navigation through the creation process, correlating technique with formal outcomes while preserving the imperfections and adaptations that characterize the craft practice. This technical development is built to support a bigger vision, reimagining digital fabrication through holistic methods that honor human presence in technological processes, looking towards a future where digital fabrication technologies amplify rather than diminish the different human dimensions of making.

2 Current limitations of digital representation

2.1 Persistence of the Conception/Execution Division

As mentioned previously, the historical division between conception and execution has been challenged by maker movements and digital fabrication, yet it persists despite these advances. Digital representation formats constitute one of the most evident examples of how this division continues to manifest itself in contemporary practice. While these formats enable the translation of ideas into physical artifacts, they simultaneously reinforce the separation between design thinking and material execution that has characterized industrial production since the 19th century.

While the democratization of digital fabrication technologies in maker spaces has given people access to manufacturing methods previously available only to large industrial companies, an unthinkable development 20 years ago, this proximity to manufacturing has happened through human adaptation to the machines, not the other way around. Despite unprecedented access to manufacturing promising to reconnect makers with the full creative process, personal fabrication has primarily democratized the tools of production through "non-industrial" scaled-down versions at reduced costs, without challenging how we interact with these machines or represent creative knowledge.

Current digital representation and manufacturing formats often perpetuate this division of labor described by Neil Gershenfeld (2023) as a "historical error" because current representation and

manufacturing formats have barely evolved since their inception. While digital fabrication promises to reconnect designers with materials, the representations used in these processes remain fundamentally disconnected from general knowledge and practice, reflecting what Lucy Suchman identifies as the persistent separation between "subjects and objects" in technological design. Current formats treat makers as disembodied minds operating on passive materials, failing to capture the "relational character of our capacities for action" (Suchman, 2009), the embodied knowledge that emerges through material engagement.

2.2 File Format Limitations

The technical architecture of current digital representation formats exemplifies the disconnect between human creativity and machine execution that William Morris identified over a century ago. As the author observed, there's a lack of empathy between the designer and the man who executes the design. More than a century later, this observation remains relevant in digital contexts, where standard file formats perpetuate this disconnection.

G-code, the primary language used to control CNC machines and 3D printers, reduces complex creative processes to a series of coordinates and mechanical instructions (like "G1 X10 Y20" to move to a specific position, or "M104 S205" to set a 3D printer's temperature). These file formats reduce complex artifacts to geometric abstractions. STL (STereolithography) files, a standard format used in 3D printing for over 30 years, represent objects as collections of triangular faces defined by coordinates. While STL can mathematically draw a "precise" representation of an object, this representation shows nothing of how an object came to be, the decisions made during its creation, or the knowledge embedded in its form.

Even with the appearance of newer alternatives like .3MF, a format developed by industry leaders capable of storing additional information such as color, material properties, and metadata beyond just mesh geometry, these representations still fail to bridge the critical gap between conception and execution. They capture what to make, but not how or why.

Figure 1: Mesh format in shaded and wireframe view (Image created by the author)

This results in a paradox: personal fabrication that theoretically could reunite conception and execution instead perpetuates their separation through representation formats that prioritize machine efficiency over human understanding and engagement. On a manufacturing aspect, these formats tend to present an idealized fabrication scenario. When instructing a 3D printer to print a PLA (Polylactic acid) part at 205 degrees (following manufacturer guidelines), there's a placement of trust in the machine to execute correctly. The reality of fabrication, however, frequently deviates from this idealization when materials behave unpredictably or machines encounter physical limitations not accounted for in the digital model.

The geometric model contains no provision for adaptation or response to these real-world variables, qualities that are central to craftship. Unlike a craftsman who can adjust technique in response to

material feedback, these formats lock users into rigid execution paths disconnected from material and tangible realities.

2.3 Software Fragmentation

This situation is aggravated by current standardized workflows for operating digital fabrication machines, which are unnecessarily complicated for non-industrialized contexts. Users must navigate between Computer Aided Design software and their representations, Computer Aided Manufacturing software, usually machine model specific, and then load these files onto the machine while interacting with its specific controls. This lack of communication between humans, machines, and software further perpetuates the division between design and making.

In recent years, there have been explorations of synergies between CAD and CAM, especially in 3D printing areas. Thanks to the implementation of visual programming modules in 3D software, such as **Grasshopper** inside **Rhino**, a parametric design tool that uses node-based programming, **Geometry Nodes** inside **Blender**, a procedural modeling system for creating complex geometries, or Nadya Peek and Neil Gershenfeld's **Mods CE**, a browser-based environment for machine control, there have been many explorations, primarily *community-driven*, on how to transfer designs to machine instructions without going through diverse interfaces or software. As Peek and Gershenfeld observe, "Software is shared through files and libraries, but workflows are not" (Peek & Gershenfeld, 2018), highlighting the limitation of how knowledge is shared and preserved. Even though these approaches favor more human interactions with machines by eliminating the CAD to CAM transition, there's still a huge gap that needs to be bridged, particularly in capturing and sharing the specific workflows that makers develop for specific machines, materials, and design contexts.

Figure 2: 3D printing workflow. From "Generating 3D printing files (G-code) with Grasshopper" by M. Ozdemir, Z. Doubrovski, & J. Martinez Castro, 2024. In the public domain.

Figure 3: Grasshopper to g-code example (Image created by the author)

The evolution of digital file formats mirrors our changing technological needs. As manufacturing contexts evolved beyond mere efficiency, representation systems adapted accordingly, STL giving way to OBJ for

color and material representation, then to FBX for character animation, and more recently to 3MF. This progression suggests the potential for new formats that might better align with our contemporary context. Yet the current technological environment, characterized by the increasing dehumanization and separation of design from fabrication, lacks voices advocating for more human-centered approaches to digital fabrication, approaches that can preserve creator identity and individuality. With this goal, looking at the resilience and wisdom embedded in traditional craft traditions might highlight new pathways for bridging this divide, reconnecting conception with execution in ways that honor both technological advancement and human creativity.

2.4 Beyond Current Limitations: Alternative Approaches

This reconnection of conception and execution requires a rethinking of how the essence of creation itself can be captured. It's necessary to question how data can truly represent the formation process of a product. Current parametric design software offers "operation trees" that allow users to see the design process in sequential steps, but these linear representations fail to capture iterations and evolutions, tactile knowledge, or material adaptations that characterize design and prototyping processes.

Figure 4: Solidworks Operation Tree (Image created by the author)

A promising alternative approach can be found in documentation platforms like those used by Fabacademy and Fabricademy students, global distributed education programs focused on rapid prototyping through digital fabrication and new technologies applied to textiles and wearables, which preserve not just final results but entire creative journeys. Unlike operation trees that reduce creation to mechanical sequences, these platforms showcase detailed thoughts, reflections, failures, and fabrication processes, creating rich narratives of creative agency that go beyond mere representation or fabrication files and potentially offering greater value in preserving process knowledge.

Artisanship offers valuable insights in this respect. An example is the practice of pottery wheel, where the artisan manipulates a block of clay, adding and removing material, modifying its composition during the manufacturing process, and reworking it. The artisanal process represents a continuous evolution not perceived as iterations of a project but as a holistic approach, where continuous learning and personal experience of the creative process shape the results. This evolution, based on learning and experience, stretches over time, a characteristic that standard digital fabrication representation formats overlook. G-code, as a clear example of it, does take into account this fourth dimension of time, but does it based on

the perfection and idealization that characterizes industrial fabrication, disregarding the identity of who manufactures and why they do it.

While current formats perpetuate this division, craftspeople, rather than accepting the constraints of industrial-oriented technologies, are reimagining how digital tools can serve more human-centered creative processes. This emerging approach represents not a rejection of technology but a thoughtful integration that preserves the essential qualities of craftship while leveraging digital capabilities. Unlike the one-way adaptation that has characterized personal fabrication, where humans adjust to machine requirements, *neo-craftsmanship* suggests a bidirectional relationship where technology and craft knowledge mutually inform and enhance each other.

3 Neo-craftship

The historical divide between conception and execution that has characterized industrial production might suggest that traditional craft practices would be fundamentally incompatible with digital fabrication technologies. However, evidence shows a completely different narrative, one of remarkable adaptation and resilience within the craft communities. Far from rejecting technological innovation, many craftspeople have thoughtfully incorporated digital tools into their practice while maintaining the creative agency that defines craftsmanship.

Evidence of this adaptation comes from *Understanding the New Technological Context for Craftsmanship*, a study carried out by *The European Crafts Alliance* and *Ohayō* in 2025. The research reveals that 69.70% of surveyed craftspeople have integrated digital tools for design or fabrication technologies into their practice, with 76.74% reporting that this integration made their products more competitive in the marketplace. Adoption spans various technologies, including CAD (51.16%), 3D printing (41.86%), laser cutting (37.21%), and CNC machining (32.56%).

This integration is significant considering these technologies were originally designed for industrialized contexts, where separation is standard practice as jobs are divided and specialized. Their interfaces, workflows, and representation formats reflect this industrial heritage, often assuming specialized technical knowledge and standardized production processes that could seem contradictory to craft methodologies.

This adaptation of craftspeople showcases how tacit knowledge persists even within technological contexts, with agency being "relational, dynamic, and collective rather than inherent in specific network elements" (Suchman, 2009), craftspeople maintain their embodied knowledge by creating new configurations of agency that include digital tools.

This phenomenon, often referred to as *neo-craftship*, provides a valuable framework for understanding this evolution. According to *La nueva artesanía. Tradición, tecnología y creatividad*, *neo-craftship* goes beyond "the convergence between craft techniques and modern technologies in the creation processes" (Esteve et al., 2023). What distinguishes it is the preservation of creative agency throughout the process. In this approach, material knowledge, embodied expertise, and technological capabilities coexist and inform each other.

By adapting to become more competitive in a consumption-based system without losing their craft essence, artisans demonstrate that more human-centered approaches to digital fabrication are possible. The craft sector's resilience stems not from resistance to change but from thoughtful adaptation that preserves agency within the technological context. By examining how craftspeople maintain their creative voice while using digital tools, new pathways for representation formats that honor the human elements of creation could be identified.

4 Redefining preservation: Cross-cultural models and approaches

4.1 From Material to Intangible Heritage

Neocraftsmanship and its adaptive evolution highlights the need to effectively preserve not just the physical artifacts of craft but the embodied knowledge, processes, and creative decision-making that define these practices. As craftspeople integrate digital tools into their workflows, there's a need to develop new approaches to preserve the intangible dimensions of craft that transcend mere technical production. As traditional approaches to preservation that have primarily focused on maintaining physical objects in their original material form have proved to be inadequate for capturing the dynamic, evolving nature of craft knowledge in this new technological context, contemporary preservation efforts should look to cross-cultural models that have successfully preserved living traditions through adaptation rather than static conservation.

The 2003 **UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage** marked a shift in preservation paradigms by officially recognizing that cultural heritage extends beyond physical monuments to include practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, and skills that communities recognize as part of their cultural identity. The text defines intangible cultural heritage as something that is "*constantly recreated by communities and groups in response to their environment*" (UNESCO, 2003), highlighting its living, evolving nature. This perspective directly challenges traditional preservation approaches that aim to freeze artifacts in time, instead emphasizing transmission and adaptation as essential preservation mechanisms.

In order to connect these emerging preservation "philosophies" with the preservation of creative agency in this digital context, it is valuable to examine alternative methods of non-material preservation that exist across different cultural contexts.

4.2 Adaptive Preservation Models Across Cultures

Cuban Automobile Preservation: Functionality Through Adaptation

The preservation of classic American automobiles in Cuba represents a compelling model of adaptive preservation born of necessity. Following Fidel Castro's Cuban Revolution in 1959 and the subsequent U.S. embargo, Cubans were faced with no access to new vehicles or original parts to maintain all these automobiles.

There are an estimated 60,000 classic American cars in Cuba. About half of the cars originate from the 1950s, while 25 percent are from the 1940s and another 25 percent are from the 1930s. A lot of them have been passed down from generation to generation, along with the mechanical genius. (Diplomatic Times, 2019)

Through adaptation and resilience, these automobiles have been kept running by their owners. The external shells maintain their historical appearance and cultural significance, while internally, these vehicles have evolved into hybrid assemblages. Substitutions on the cars usually are "*diesel engines for the old straight-six or V-8 engines originally in the cars, due to diesel's lower cost on the island, and the better fuel efficiency of the engines*" (Diplomatic Times, 2019), although it's not unusual for some of the engines to be replaced by diesel engines from Soviet trucks or boats.

This approach prioritizes ongoing functionality and cultural continuity over strict material authenticity. These cars remain culturally important, not despite their adaptations but because of them, embodying Cuban resilience, innovation, and creativity.

Today, Cuba is still home to thousands of classic cars. Many of them are used as taxis, especially in Havana. These cars, with their glossy paint jobs and rumbling engines, are a major draw for tourists. While some people might expect these old cars to be museum pieces, they're part of everyday life in Cuba. (Adewale, 2024)

Whanganui River: Relational Preservation Through Legal Personhood

While the Cuban model demonstrates adaptive preservation through material modification, New Zealand's approach to the Whanganui River exemplifies preservation through transformed legal and conceptual frameworks. The legal recognition of New Zealand's Whanganui River as a living entity with "the same rights and responsibilities as a person" (Pāremata Aotearoa, 2017) represents a reimagination of preservation based on Indigenous Māori perspectives.

Rather than treating the river as a natural resource to be protected through conservation and regulations, thanks to this approach, *"the Maori are now empowered to manage and protect the river based on their traditional ecological knowledge"* (VijayKuma, 2019). The 2017 legislation that granted the river legal personhood emerged from Māori understanding that they do not own the river, even its name, ***Awa Tupua***, does not represent property, *"it includes the whole river system, its spirit, and the people that are related to it"* (National Library of New Zealand, 2017), expressed in the saying "Ko au te awa, ko te awa ko au" (I am the river, and the river is me).

This model of preservation focuses on maintaining relationships rather than controlling physical resources. It recognizes that preservation must account for living connections and ongoing interactions, not just physical attributes.

These contrasting but complementary approaches, one emphasizing material adaptation while the other relational continuity, showcase shared principles that offer insights into the digital craft preservation practice.

4.3 Principles for Digital Craft Preservation

These diverse approaches to preservation share common principles, they prioritize process over product, relationships over artifacts, and adaptation over *stasis*. Extrapolating these principles to the challenge of preserving creative agency in digital contexts, these models might suggest that effective digital representation formats should capture process knowledge and decision-making rather than just final geometries, preserve the dynamic relationship between maker, material, and tool, and allow for adaptation and evolution rather than freezing techniques in time.

This aligns with the aforementioned ***UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage***:

'Safeguarding' means measures aimed at ensuring the viability of the intangible cultural heritage, including the identification, documentation, research, preservation, protection, promotion, enhancement, transmission, particularly through formal and non-formal education, as well as the revitalization of the various aspects of such heritage. (UNESCO, 2003)

Just as Cuban mechanics transform cars while maintaining their cultural significance, and just as the Māori maintain their relationship with the Whanganui River through evolving practices, neo-craftsmanship demonstrates how technology can be incorporated into living traditions without sacrificing their essential character. However, current digital preservation methods remain inadequate for capturing the intangible dimensions of craft.

Existing digital preservation techniques typically focus on documenting the physical attributes of objects through 3D scanning, photography, or detailed measurements. While these approaches excel at recording material properties, they fail to capture the embodied knowledge, decision-making processes, and creative agency of craftsmanship. Traditional documentation methods like written records or video recordings provide partial glimpses into the process but struggle to *store* the tacit knowledge embedded in craft practices.

Furthermore, conventional digital preservation treats objects as static entities, preserving them as they exist at a single moment in time rather than as elements in an evolving tradition. This approach misaligns

with the nature of craft knowledge, which is inherently adaptive, responsive, and continuously developing through practice.

The limitations of current preservation technologies point to a need for new digital methods specifically designed to preserve intangible aspects of craft. These methods must go beyond mere documentation to create dynamic, interactive representations that capture not just what craft objects are, but how they come to be, why specific decisions are made during their creation, and how craft traditions evolve while maintaining their essential character. Developing such methods represents not just a technological challenge but a conceptual shift in how cultural heritage is valued and understood in the digital age.

5 Experiment design, implementation, and goals

5.1 From Form-Making to Form-Finding

The limitations of current digital representation extend beyond technical constraints to fundamental conceptual approaches. Traditional CAD systems predominantly emphasize a *form-making* approach, a process where designers manipulate idealized geometric primitives toward predetermined outcomes. In contrast, craft processes approaches enable *form-finding*, where form emerges through discovery, material engagement, and responsive adaptation.

Form-making, loosely defined, is a process of inspiration and refinement (form precedes analysis of programmatic influences and design constraints) versus form-finding as (loosely) a process of discovery and editing (form emerges from analysis). (Tedeschi, 2014)

This distinction represents a shift from manipulating discrete geometric objects to defining dynamic relationships between elements, marking a conceptual transition from "what" to "how".

5.2 Sensing Temporal Evolution in Craft Processes

The methodology proposed in this research is based on a *form-finding* ideal, capturing how an artifact changes over time, based on experience and knowledge-based decisions, adding a fourth dimension to preservation that static approaches don't address. By establishing direct contact with artisans and practitioners and recording their practice, this research documents not just the final artifact but the complete journey of its creation.

For this case study, pottery wheel practitioners were selected due to the visible transformation of material in their craft and the clear relationship between hand gestures and formal outcomes, offering a scenario where clay visibly responds to pressure, movement, and technique, making the embodied knowledge "observable".

Figure 4: Pottery-making process (Image created by the author)

5.3 Technical Implementation

The technical implementation employs a multi-modal computer vision pipeline designed to capture the temporal evolution of craft knowledge through material transformation. The methodology centers on establishing correlations between embodied gestures and their material outcomes, creating a linked representation of the creative process.

Video Capture and Analysis

The pottery creation process is recorded using a single camera positioned to capture both the changing clay form and the artisan's gesture techniques. This non-intrusive approach looks to preserve the natural working rhythm while generating the dataset. Each video frame undergoes automated segmentation analysis using **Segment Anything Model 2 (SAM2)** to isolate the clay form from its surroundings, while depth mapping through **Depth Anything V2** reconstructs the three-dimensional qualities of the piece at each temporal moment.

Volumetric Reconstruction

The segmented images and depth maps are processed through Neural Radiance Fields, a neural network architecture that represents scenes as continuous volumetric functions rather than discrete geometric primitives. Unlike traditional mesh-based reconstructions that interpolate between vertices, NeRFs encode the entire volume as learned density and color functions, enabling the capture of surface variations, texture irregularities, and the organic deformations of pottery. This volumetric approach preserves the non-idealized qualities of tangible craft representation.

Gesture-Form Correlation

MediaPipe hand tracking algorithm creates a parallel dataset of gestural landmarks that are synchronized with the material transformations. This correlation methodology enables the system to establish relationships between specific hand movements and resulting changes in clay form, documenting the embodied knowledge transfer from artisan to material.

Figure 5: Pointcloud generated based on depth map values. (Image created by the author)

5.4 File Format Synthesis

The resulting multi-modal data streams get compiled into the custom `.cft` using a **Python** based system built with **zlib** and **JSON** serialization. This custom format packages the temporal NeRF representations, gesture landmarks, and metadata into a single compressed file that results not in a static 3D model but in a time based, interactive representation that maintains a relation between gestures input and the material response.

The resulting approach enables temporal navigation, allowing users to move forward and backward through the creation process, observing how the form emerges and evolves, providing technique visualization where hand and pose positions, and movements are visualized in relation to the changing form, making explicit the "invisible" relationship between technique and outcome. Unlike conventional CAD models that represent "perfect", idealized forms, this new format `.cft` delivers a "non-idealized" representation that preserves the imperfections, corrections, and evolution that characterizes craft.

Figure 6: `.cft` format (Image created by the author)

6 Application and use

6.1 Experimental Setup

The application of the proposed methodology was conducted with a group of four pottery artisans of varying experience levels (one master craftsman, one mid-career artisan with around 5 years of experience, and turntable aficionados with 2 or fewer years of practice). This diverse group allowed for a

comparative analysis of how different levels of expertise manifest in both material outcomes and procedural approaches.

Unlike a "controlled laboratory experiment", this study deliberately recorded artisans in their natural working environments, personal studios, and workshops. Each artisan used their personal approaches, tools, and techniques rather than standardized materials or techniques, as this approach acknowledged that craft knowledge is deeply contextual and embedded within personal environments and preferences.

Figure 7: Three representations of the pottery-making process. a) A person working on a potter's wheel. b) A depthmap visualization of the pottery-making process. c) A grayscale or depth map representation of the same pottery-making process. (Images created by the author)

Figure 8: Visualization of pottery-making process with segmentation. a) A person working at a potter's wheel, overlaying an orange shape over the clay piece segmented on the wheelbase. b) A segmentation mask isolating a specific element of the pottery-making process. (Images created by the author)

During the experiment, approximately 4000 frames were collected per session, with each session lasting between 15-20 minutes. The resulting frames went through the process previously mentioned in the Technical Implementation section and produced the following outputs:

- Depth maps of each frame were generated using the **Depth Anything V2** model
- Frames with object segmentation masks using **Segment Anything Model 2 (SAM2)**
- JSON file of hand motion tracking landmarks per frame using **MediaPipe**
- Neural Radiance Fields per each frame representing the tridimensional model segmented.

Figure 9: Pottery-making process with hand motion applied (Image created by the author)

6.2 Representation Outcomes

In order to let the users explore the correlation of hand tracking with clay forms custom *Grasshopper* components are developed to decompress and visualize the *.crft* file within *Rhinceros 3D*. These components automatically decompress the archive, parse the temporal data streams, and generate interactive visualizations where hand tracking landmarks are represented as spheres and cylinders positioned in 3D space. The NeRF volumetric data is converted to detailed meshes using the marching cubes algorithm for each temporal frame, while the original video frames are projected as point clouds to provide additional spatial context, enabling navigation through the temporal sequence, allowing to observe the synchronized representation of gesture, form, and material response. Early feedback from the artisans participating suggested promising applications for the technique learning.

Figure 10: *.crft* file opened in Grasshopper visualization of hand position and clay shape in frame 52 (Image created by the author)

Figure 11: .crft file opened in Grasshopper visualization of hand position and clay shape in frame 50 (Image created by the author)

The resulting *.crft* format establishes a different relationship between digital representation and material reality by prioritizing process over product, and acknowledging the dialogue between maker and material. Rather than attempting to eliminate the human elements of creation as conventional formats often do, this approach intentionally foregrounds them, preserving the maker's voice throughout the representation.

7 Experiment limitations and future approaches

The methodology presented in this research showcased an exploratory vision for preserving embodied knowledge in digital formats. Several technical limitations were encountered during the implementation that highlight the challenges in this domain and suggest newer directions for a future reimplementation.

7.1 Single Camera Constraints

The use of a single camera for data capture limited the quality of the 3D reconstructions. Although this approach was chosen to maintain a non-intrusive documentation method that wouldn't disrupt the craftspeople's working processes, it created challenges for accurate 3D representations. Since single-view capture cannot observe occluded portions of the shape, the OpenLRM (Large Reconstruction Model) framework was employed to predict a complete 3D geometry from individual frames. OpenLRM uses a transformer-based architecture to directly generate Neural Radiance Fields from single input images, enabling generalization across diverse object types. However, this approach introduces potential inaccuracies when compared to multi-view reconstruction methods, as the model's probabilistic predictions about the current use case may not reflect accurate shapes during the craft process.

7.2 Material Properties and Hand Tracking Challenges

The choice of pottery as the case study, while beneficial for its visible material transformation, introduced challenges for hand tracking. Fingers covered in clay frequently caused tracking failures in the MediaPipe hand landmark detection system. As the artisans worked, clay accumulation on their hands created occlusions that interrupted the continuity of gesture tracking. For future iterations, alternative tracking methods or supplementary sensors might be necessary for these kinds of scenarios.

7.3 Computational Resource Constraints

The processing pipeline was significantly constrained by available computational resources. Using a MacBook Pro M2 Pro with 10 cores (6 performance and 4 efficiency) and 16GB of RAM, the system struggled with real-time processing of high-resolution video frames. Ending up needing batch processing of segments, introducing noise and inconsistencies in the resulting segmentations.

7.4 Format efficiency

The creation of the `.cft` format from scratch resulted in inefficient data structures and excessively large file sizes. Without optimization techniques to this new representation approach, the resulting files became impractical for use and sharing.

7.5 Software Integration Limitations

While Grasshopper became a flexible platform for developing interactive visualization components, it demonstrated efficiency limitations when handling the data generated. The necessity to convert Neural Radiance Fields representations to mesh models using the marching cubes algorithm for Grasshopper compatibility reduced the fidelity of the original volumetric data. This conversion was necessary as Grasshopper does not natively support NeRF visualization or manipulation.

8 Conclusion

This research has explored how digital representation formats might evolve to preserve creative agency and embodied knowledge in design and fabrication processes. Through speculative experimentation, this work has highlighted the limitations of current approaches while imagining human-centered alternatives.

The standard representation formats that dominate digital fabrication today are products of an industrial paradigm that systematically excludes the human elements of creation. The speculative approach developed in this research suggests that it's needed not to accept these constraints as inevitable. By shifting from static representation to dynamic process capture, it's possible to begin to envision systems that preserve rather than eliminate embodied knowledge.

The main conclusion from this research is that fabrication in maker spaces and Fablabs should intentionally diverge from industrial fabrication methods. While they share technologies, they serve different purposes. Industrial fabrication prioritizes consistency and efficiency, values encoded in its formats and workflows. Personal fabrication spaces should prioritize learning, experimentation, and personal expression.

The "democratization" of digital fabrication has predominantly focused on making industrial machines more accessible through reduced cost and size. True democratization must go beyond hardware accessibility to address creative agency. It's not possible to claim to have democratized fabrication if machines have merely been scaled down without changing how humans interact with them.

The historical division between conception and execution continues to influence personal fabrication practices. Overcoming this division requires more holistic approaches that draw wisdom from traditional artisanship, where thinking and making remain unified. Live machine control systems represent a promising direction for reconnecting conception and execution. As noted in the *Modular-Things* research, "Rather than 'embedding' a high-level language into hardware, we are 'lifting' hardware modules into a high-level language. This lift allows us to shift application-specific code out of hardware systems and into a friendlier programming environment" (Read et al, 2023). These systems enable real-time interaction and adaptation rather than relegating creators to file preparers who passively observe machine execution. By eliminating the tedious workflow transitions between CAD, CAM, and machine control, these approaches restore the continuous feedback loop between creator and material that characterizes craft processes.

Perhaps the most significant insight is that preserving embodied knowledge in the digital age requires preserving the maker's voice throughout the creation process. As exposed through the paper, current

formats systematically erase this voice, reducing rich creative processes to standardized instructions. This research suggests an alternative vision, digital representation systems that honor human presence within technological processes.

It's important to note that this work does not pretend to offer a definitive solution but invites to reconsider how we represent creative knowledge in digital contexts. The future of personal fabrication lies not in a more perfect reproduction of industrial paradigms at smaller scales, but in developing new paradigms that better align with the human dimensions of making, where conception and execution are reunited, the process is valued alongside the outcome, and embodied knowledge is preserved alongside technical specifications.

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